

EDITORIAL POLICY

Journal of Education and Society (JES) is the Peer-Reviewed journal of the Leyte Normal University published annually. JES envisions itself as a space of conversation in the teaching and learning of all disciplines and the interactions within and among communities (i.e., teachers, learners, professionals, indigenous peoples). We see the journal as an avenue to engage in knowledge production, expansion, and exchange, where ideas are proposed, and where long-held assumptions are contested.

JES subthemes are mainly the following: teaching & learning, policy & implementation, critical literacy, development of pedagogies, instructional materials (IMs), IMs support materials, measurement and evaluation, K to 12 educations, higher education, special education, professional education, education technology, tech-voc education, online education, distance education alternative education, indigenous people (IP) education. Researchers, scholars, and educators are invited to submit research and theoretical papers to the journal for consideration.

To guide your manuscript preparation, here are the journal's *Guidelines for Authors*:

1. Articles should be original and must not be under consideration for any other publication.
2. Articles should be as long as 4,000 to 6,000 words from Introduction to Conclusion. Longer articles will be returned to the authors for trimming.
3. The parts of the paper are as follows:

Title

Abstract of 150-200 words

Keywords of 5-10 words

Introduction which includes background, problem and purpose of study (1-2 pages)

Literature Review citing journals and books but more of journal articles, which should be at least 20 and 50% of which were published within the last 10 years (3-6 pages)

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework (1 page)

Research Questions

Methodology

Design
Sampling
Data Collection and Instruments
Data Analysis
Ethical Considerations
Reflexivity (applies to qualitative research only)

Results and Discussion

Conclusion

Acknowledgement (optional)

References

4. In keeping with the spirit of the different areas in education, our journal seeks to bring research knowledge to a broader audience from various disciplines.

5. Manuscripts should be double-spaced except for notes and list of references, which should be single-spaced. Articles must be typed in Times New Roman, size 12, and with one-inch margin on all sides in an A4 paper.

6. All theoretical manuscript must have the following:

- Title
- Abstract
- Introduction
- 3 to 6 major sections
- Conclusion

7. Notes, tables, graphs, photographs, illustrations, and figures should be kept at a minimum.

8. References and in-text citations should strictly follow the American Psychological Association (APA) 6th edition.

9. The journal follows a double-blind refereeing system. As such, all references to the author's identity must be removed in the article, notes, and list of references.

10. Authors are responsible for securing all the necessary permits for any part of the article copyrighted to someone else. Articles, once published, are copyrighted to the Leyte Normal University. A Form for Transfer of Copyright will be required of the author to sign. It is understood that corresponding author has secured prior approval from co-authors about the copyright transfer.

11. **Manuscripts should be submitted in doc or docx files as email attachment to jes@lnu.edu.ph or register at www.lnu.edu.ph/lnujournals/index.php/jes. Then make a NEW SUBMISSION.**

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